

Agroforestry as a Farming Approach

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Initial development stages of alley cropping at Lill-Nägels Agroforestry Pilot Farm in Southern Finland (Photo: Tanja Kähkönen).

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Soil health degradation can be tackled with regenerative farming. Whereas for instance wind and water erosion linked to soil organic matter soils degrade soil health, regenerative farming has the potential to improve soil health and increase soil carbon stocks. Regenerative farming includes practices such as grazing, manure management, minimal tillage, permanent soil cover, crop diversification, soil amendment, bio-stimulation, and agroforestry. Agroforestry is, thus, itself a regenerative farming and land use practice associated to agroecological practices.

No specific certification exists for regenerative farming in Finland. One of the organisations advancing regenerative farming in Finland is the *Baltic Sea Action Group (BSAG)* which has developed general regenerative farming criteria for farms in collaboration with stakeholders, namely farmers, researchers and companies. The criteria are composed of eight components: 1) Continuous development of competencies and operations, 2) purposefully improving and maintaining soil health, 3) biodiversity above and below ground systematically reinforced, 4) diverse crop rotation, 5) maximization of all-year-round, living vegetation cover, 6) minimisation of tillage, 7) nutrient use based on plant needs and relying on organic fertilisers and biological nitrogen fixation, and 8) minimisation of the use of plant protection products (herbicides, biocides, etc). The criteria aim at supporting farmers' and companies' understanding regenerative farming.

In Finland, the most common regenerative benefits of agroforestry are wind and water erosion reduction, biodiversity increase (pollinating insects), water bodies quality increase, carbon storage, microclimate improvement, nutrient cycling improvement, and nutrient leaching reduction. *Kilpiä Farm* and *Lill-Nägels Agroforestry Pilot Farm* in Southern Finland are clear examples of agroforestry that can be upscaling in Finland.

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